

Country Joy

by

Tom Heston

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V1
Allegro C F C

I want-ed to grow up to be a cow-boy to rope cattle and ride the great-est

G C F C G7

bulls and then I real-ized that it's all deep down in-side in my heart Coun-try Joy is ev-ery-

R1
C G7 C C F C

where. For it's LEFT RIGHT LEFT RIGHT dance a-cross the stage! Dos-ey do turn and skip a-

G C F

round be-cause the love is deep in-side it fills up all my life Coun-try

R2

C G7 C G7 C C F C

Joy mus-ic danc-ing ev-ery where. - So here we are! Here we go! In Jes-us-'s arms we

G C F C G7 C

stay. So here we are! Here we go! The Coun-try Joy fills my heart ev-ery day!

V2: I wanted to grow up to be a cowgirl
to ride horses and run barrels at the fair
And then I realized that it's all deep down inside
In my heart country joy is everywhere. => R1 => V3

V3: Today I always wear my COWBOY BOOTS
At the office or in the theater
Because the country fills my life it makes everything all right
Country Joy! Music, dancing everywhere. => R1 => R2.

*Then Jesus held the children in his
arms. He laid his hands upon them
and blessed them. - Mark 10:16*

Country Joy is one of those songs that came to me spontaneously out of nowhere. Or maybe it came out of everywhere, I'm not sure. What I do know is that one Sunday morning, at twilight, just before 5 am I woke up with this song playing in my head. Instantly, I thought, what a wonderful day! I then got up, not at all tired but rather quite energized, wrote the song down on paper, and the song hasn't changed hardly a bit since that initial moment.

I remain curious as to where this song came from, as I was raised in the city, have only ridden a horse a few of times, and as a child hardly ever played cowboy but rather wanted to be a truck driver. I prefer tennis shoes over cowboy boots and have line danced maybe once or twice. So why did I wake up with this thought that growing up I wanted to be a cowboy? Curious, but certainly it was a joyful thought.

After reflection, the message this song has given me is that all of our days can be full of joy. As a physician, I have had many challenging days bursting with the emotional stress of seeing people sick, some tragically so. For many, nobody could alter the course of their condition. Yet even in these moments of greatest effort to help the patient in front of me, I have had by necessity an underlying sense of hope and optimism; a deep seated belief that my efforts and my presence would somehow help that specific patient. That ultimately my actions would repercuss and help the wider community. I believe that serious people, in serious situations, can and should have an unshakable faith in the goodness of life. We need to have an indomitable joie de vie. Country joy is for all of us.

I have been greatly blessed to have found my calling, yet this is in no way unique. Rather, all jobs, all tasks, all human activity can be ennobled by joy. For example, a janitor I work with brings such a pleasant attitude with him every day that the entire medical ward's spirits are consistently uplifted. To me, he is the spiritual leader of the unit, and his presence makes all of us perform better, and our patients get healthier faster. Life can be challenging, but music helps us get through the tough times with optimism and joy.

- TFH 7/24/2019